

Exploring Hegel's Concept of Self-Realization in Arthur Miller's *Death of a Salesman*

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Abstract

What is Hegelian Self-Realization and how it can be achieved; is the basic phenomenon in this research. This research explores the Hegel's concept of Self-Realization in Arthur Miller's play *Death of a Salesman*. The main issue that is being discussed here is that, how a man realizes himself, gets basic knowledge and realizes his inner self to enjoy a superior life. Therefore this research will explore the mental and psychological behavior of the characters of the play about their self. This research discusses the journey of characters of *Death of a Salesman*. The study focuses on the protagonist's journey towards the search of self. It also founds that Self-Realization needs a proper knowledge and care about individual's personality. The protagonist Willy Loman makes a long journey, does a job for which he wonders in different cities because one who tries to seek truth about his personality put his life in trouble. As he aware about the reality of the social harshness then he becomes more and more restricted about his self. When protagonist gets full knowledge about the reality of the society and about his personality then he thinks that it is better to die than to live.

Keywords: Self-Realization, Knowledge, Psychological, Truth, Journey, Reality, Society, Personality, Death

1. Introduction

Death of the Salesman is Arthur Miller's charming real problems play of the society particularly of the Americans. It is also his particular play which deals with the idea of Self Realization which George Wilhelm Fredrich Hegel provided. Hegelian's self-realization discusses the knowledge about one's self and worth in the society. It enables the readers to get a clear glimpse of the concept of self realization and the troubles of men and women in America. In our society and particularly in America men and women are working like a machine. Their value decreases with the passage of time and they are thrown away like a tissue after being used. If a man realizes himself at the start of his journey then no one can play with his life.

Willy Loman, the protagonist of the *Death of a Salesman* had suffered a lot, due to lack of self knowledge. He was unaware about his early age. He was depending on Howard; the owner of the Wagnor Company, because he had served in that company for thirty four years. But the owner threw him like a trash. If he decided at the first of life and thought about him self and knew the reality of life, then he succeeded.

To bring out thematic of the play, self realization, self knowledge, reality of life and psychological sufferings of an individual and class gap are some of the themes Miller has dealt with in this play. He also dealt the sin of pride and its disastrous consequences which the protagonist had. The protagonist had the pride of his services in the company, but he was unaware about the real face of the capitalists. Due to his pride of services and good manners he had not acted upon the advice of his friends and brother who gave him idea to go abroad and change his life style. This is also the cause of his downfall.

Knowledge of roots is necessary as Frued mentioned in his book "*Traditions and Individual Discontentment*" that human beings are different from what society compels them to be because they do according to their own wish, which is motivated by pleasure principles. In *Death of a Salesman*, Miller believes that one should recognize, understand and acknowledge the forces which he governs in his life. This is necessary to live with dignity that man should not depend on others but should choose his own way himself.

As the purpose of this study is to explore the Hegelian's Self Realization in Willy Loman the character of the play *Death of a Salesman*, so the concern will be to explore the psychology and mentality of the characters. For this Roberto Assagioli argues that there are two forces which derive human. One is illusion and other is reality. In illusion a man started to see dreams and started his way but at the end when he face the reality; his all dreams go to depth. He ruined and cry for his true way of life. Same is the case with Willy Loman. More he says that self realization is the growth of awareness which is different in nature. The two important growths are psychological and maturation.

A realistic observation is that different psychological tendencies arise in ourselves which lead a man towards different directions. Self-realization is also one tendency which arises in the characters of *Death of a Salesman* particularly in Willy after a long time. Before this; under the shocks of other tendencies Willy Loman wonders the whole America. He wondered the whole America for his bright future but in actual form he was losing his worth. When at the end he reached at the knowledge of self he had ruined.

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1.1. Arthur Miller and G.W.F Hegel

Arthur Asher Miller is one of the leading figure and authoritative body in America as a playwright and essayist in 20th century in the row of Tennessee Williams and Eugene O’Neil. He was born in October 17, 1915 in Manhattan New York USA. Miller belonged to a rich and noble family. He is the second child of Isidore Miller and Augusta. Both came from Poland to America for their future. Augusta; Miller’s mother was a woman of letters. She was very cultural and intellectual lady. Due to her arrange marriage with Isidore; she remained distress for many years. Arthur Miller’s father owned a women manufacturing factory with name S.Miller and Sons. Family was very prosperous. They could afford all luxuries. In 1929 in Wall Street Crash the family’s business began to fall. Due to increasing tension in family Miller never lost his confidence. He supported the family in every way. For this he started to write short stories for newspapers. His writing career spread over a period of sixty years. During this period Miller wrote many plays and a novel *Focus* (1945), many travel journals, a collection of short stories with title *I Don’t Need You Anymore* (1967) and an autobiography entitled *Time bends a Life* (1987).

After his Graduation in Literature he started to work as a news reporter but soon he left that job and turned his idea from Journalism to English Literature. Miller focused on the social awareness with deep insight into personal weaknesses of the characters. He wrote thirty six plays in which “*No Villain*” is the first play written in 1936 and “*Finishing the Picture*” is the last play written in 2004. During this time he was awarded Pulitzer Prize for Drama. He received the Prince of Austria Award in 2002 and Jerusalem Award in 2003.

Arthur Miller’s career as a writer spread over seven decades. At the time of his death in February 10, 2005 he was considered to be the greatest dramatist of 20th century. After his death actors, directors of theaters and producers paid tribute to Miller. The University of Michigan opened the Arthur Miller Theater in March 2007. It is the only theater in the world that bears the name of Miller.

George Wilhelm Fredrich Hegel was born on august 27, 1770 in Stuttgart. In 1796 Hegel wrote “The first program for a system of German Idealism”. This book shows his ideas about self and status. His book “Phenomenology” shows the human history, wars, discoveries, scientific ideas and revolutions as an idealistic self-development of an objective spirit or mind. Hegel married Marie Von Tucher. He had three children, a daughter who died soon after her birth and two sons Karl (1813-1901) and Immanuel(1814-1891). His last published work was “The Philosophy of Right” (1821). His several works were published after his death.

1.2. The Death of a Salesman

The American Drama *Death of a Salesman* (1949) is the bright star among the works of Arthur Miller which deals with the concept of self-realization. Arthur Miller was influenced from Charles Darwin, Karl Marx, Herbert Spencer, Psychoanalytical concepts of Sigmund Freud, Carl Jung and Hegel. In modern age *The Death of a Salesman* became a universal play which focused on the individual’s thinking about religion, politics, social and economic relations. This play deals with all types of relations of a person and his thought about his personal worth in the society. In this play Miller crafted statements of psychological displacement, loss of family relations, loneliness and self-deception. Hegelian, Freudian and Jungian theories are more aligned with self. Self is the truth about one’s internal mind and thinking.

1.3. Research Questions

There have been a lot of studies on this play from different perspectives but Hegel’s concept of Self-Realization has not been explored yet. Though it is a broad area of study but this study will deal with specific questions. What the present research wants to achieve somehow modify the particular play for the concept of self realization. The present research is an attempt to find the answers of the following questions.

- What is Self-Realization from Hegelian perspective?
- How do the characters of the play *Death of a Salesman* manifest the Hegelian’s Self-Realization?
- What are the impacts of society, culture and economy on the failure of characters in the *Death of a Salesman*?

2. Literature Review

Miller’s deepest and detailed description for modern events made the play *Death of a Salesman* a more discussive piece of literature for various themes like American Dream, Absurdity, Triviality Capitalism, Expressionism and so on. Miller has painted the society in a very beautiful manner and gave birth to many questions. Therefore soon after its publication in 1969 it got the attention of many philosophers and researchers from all over the world. They analyzed it with different angels and explored its hidden meanings. Each researcher used his own subjective path to reach its destination. A brief over view of such points is given in the following lines.

Allen Lewes (1970) in his work “*American Plays and Playwrights of the Contemporary Theater*” stated the *Death of a Salesman* as a Social Play. He blamed the society and its social manners for the failure of Willy Loman. Willy is the victim of American Society that is corrupt. More he said that Miller was the follower of Capitalism. In Capitalist

society no body bears the burden of others. Willy Loman became the prey of capitalism that was the common trend in his society.

Discussing Miller's play *All My Sons* and Kris Keller's ideas Miller once remarked "I cannot live apart from the world" (Brown and Harris 1975, P.127). Same is the case with Willy Loman in *Death of a Salesman*. He entered in the complexities of the world and now tries to separate himself from the complexities for his self identity.

An Indian writer Pradhan in his work *Modern American Drama: "A study in Myth and Tradition"* says that *Death of a Salesman* is a play about dreams. Willy Loman has two dreams. One is about his business and to become a successful salesman and second is about rural life. He wants to become rich with the old customs of America but in twentieth century America has totally changed. There is no right to get more than his power. Capitalists keep the employes at their foot step. Willy is the victim of capitalism. His dream to be rich fails. Miller states that "The strongest stress on the pursuit of dreams is in *Death of a Salesman* which is a play about dreams...." The dream as a quest for paradise is embodied in Willy Loman who dreams two versions of American dream the business-urban success dream in which Willy sees himself as a magnate and the rural agrarian dream. For the success of dreams Dave Singleman, Charley and Uncle Ben are role modal (Miller 119-20). Willy Loman was the failure in his dreams before society and his family. Both dreams show the inner reality of America who does not allow to fulfill the dreams of poor and here reality of Willy is also shows "who aspires to be greater than himself". (Miller 121).

Roberts and Jacobs consider the American dream as an illusion. They state that American dream has built on false notions i-e on having well personality and well liked. They observed that the central dream of success and gaining wealth is fulfilled by selling himself. It is American policy to keep the others in illusion to hide the real face of America. It is only outer look of America that he is the mother of poor but in actual form, there people sell themselves to earn money. By selling themselves they become slaves. (p.1207). Harold Clurman extracted two meanings of dreams. One is historical dream and second is business success dream. Historical dream means having a hand to mouth job, pay bills and not having house. Business success dream means having white collar job, having enough money to meet his expenses at broad level in the decorated world. Willy Loman has achieved the historical dream. He had car, house, family and job but he was attached with business success dream.

An essay with title "A Celebration" by Joyce Carol Oates published in quarterly Review Fall 1998 and reprinted in where I've Been? And where am I going? Point out dark side of American Drama. He says that American drama is a dust in one's eyes. American society is not heart felt to the others. Nobody should blame the Willy Loman for his failure because he was the victim of that society where wealth is more important than a life. More he elaborates that in America man makes progress in a beautiful manners but when he comes back there came an earth quake which destroys all his hopes, plans and luggage. If he wants to make progress again then he starts from zero. America is like a shoe shine which disappear after some time and we have to run again for shinning. Same is the case in *Death of Salesman*.

M.W. Steinberg (1969) in his work *Arthur Miller and the Idea of Tragedy* relates Miller's plays as a tragedy. A play which has an unhappy and dreadful ending is called a tragedy but if the characters are the representors of life then it has no meaning for tragedy whether there is good ending or bad ending.(81). *Death of a Salesman* is such a play which has an unhappy ending with the tragic death of a Willy Loman. Steinberg points out that F. L. Lucas relates the tragedy as a real life. According to Lucas's point of view real life always ends with thundrical situations. Miller's characters are modern and fashionable. They are stitched in their society. Social forces of illusion which are imposed upon them are the main causes of downfall of Willy Loman. Mostly people who live a happy life face such situation in their life. Some succeed and some destroy. More Steinberg expresses that tragedy expresses the reality of a person in the world with the help of stage actions. Explaining the plays of Henric Ibsen, Steinberg also gave views about Miller. Miller is parallel with Ibsen. Their all characters show their actions on stage. Their all plays are tragic in nature. Their characters are flawless. Social injustice, social realm, social problems and social decisions affect the characters through which they come to commit such actions of tragedy. He also compares the Willy Loman the protagonist with the Greek characters. Greek characters were more tragic in their actions. He suffers due to his hamartia and his mistakes. His proud did not allow him to eradicate his mistakes.

Peter Spalding (1987) in his work *Macmillan Master Guides: Death of a Salesman* by Arthur Miller 1949 argues that Willy Loman destroyed himself due to his trivial actions. By working with his hands he degraded his value. Trivial actions lessen his strength. He would never be a salesman if he had been sincere to himself. He was more sincere to his company instead of himself and his family. The main theme of this play is that how a trivial person commit a serious crime with his trivial actions.

Adorno on Popular Culture is a famous work by R.W. Witkin published in 2003. In this work the writer made a distinction culture and mass culture. According to him mass culture is dependent on high culture. People make their ideals to the eliot class and follow their situation. If a man becomes aware about his lowerness then he accepts the fate which allows him to live. If he will not accept the fate then he will destroy. Same is the situation in *Death of a Salesman*

in which Willy Loman has set high values for himself though he was not for those values. It was his fate to be from a lower class. He was living in defective environment but when his original value came before him then he did not accept it and destroy himself.

R.W. Corrigan (1969) in his work "Arthur Miller: A Collection of Critical Essays" says that Miller talks about two passions in a man. First one is "passion to feel" and second is "passion to know". In *Death of a Salesman* there exists a passion to know. Play compels us to know more and more about our self and society rather than to feel. The passage of Willy Loman's life is to know about his society. We have no fixed ending point in our life. Our example is like a puppet in the air (pp.61).

Terrey Eagleton (2001) in an essay with title "Marxism and Literary Criticism" consider the *Death of a Salesman* as a capitalistic play. According to him cultural and industry products are producing ideas which are related with capitalism. Capitalism is a system in which capital remains in the hands of people. Every person gets his share according to his struggle. In capital society no body bears the burden of others. Capitalist society is the society of competition. If a person wants to earn more and more then he should work hard instead of trusting on others. Willy Loman was the victim of capitalist society. Capitalism is the main cause of Willy's death.

Dr. Ashok B. Yawale in his work "Intra Social Conflict in *Death of Salesman*" argues that Miller showed the image of American industrial society. He more explains that industrial revolution in America demolished the family relations and sincerity and created depression among people. And this is not the case of a single person but of the whole America in which people work like machine without taking care of others. Miller elaborates the Americans' nature through his characters. Willy Loman was living in America but he could not understand the reality. He was expecting benefits from his employer which was wrong to capitalistic nature of Americans. Tom F. Driver in his work *Strength and Weakness in Arthur Miller* expresses the *Death of a Salesman* in these words "We cannot judge wheather the fault is in Willy or society". On one side Miller wants universal morality while on the other side he writes about man's ability and limitations which lie within a man himself. (p. 17)

John Beaufort the critic for the *Christian Science Monitor* blames Willy as a passive person. Miller spoke about the values of his society but Willy's values were false. In a competitive society false values and decisions cannot lead towards goal. Willy has no self power of decision but he has an idea that salesman ship is only and one way of success. Guth Hans in his work "Tragedy and the Common Man" illustrates Aristotle's definition of tragedy that "it is an imitation through actions rather than narrating a serious, complete and ample actions". This drama is a tragedy of a salesman who works with his hands. Willy tries his best to survive but his fate lead him towards the tragic scene of life in the shape of suicide. Miller believes that common man is a good subject for tragedy like kings. Tragedy is the result of man's struggle to evaluate himself properly. It is the nature of a man to evaluate himself with his competitor. Willy's competitor was Charley. Charley reached at his destination. His sons got good positions in society while Willy remains poor and his sons could not succeed. Willy fails to evaluate himself which is the major cause of his failure.

Terry Otten (2002) '*The Temptation of Innocence in the Dramas of Arthur Miller* explains the conflict between innocence and personal liability. Through the character of Willy Loman, Miller tries to find innocence in the life of people. Miller also examined the relationship between society and individual. Some autobiographical elements in the play show the Miller's self experience in his society. (p.02). Miller wondered here and there in search of his livelihood in the start of his practical life. He made his own way of success but no one took pity on him. Same is the case with Willy Loman. That employer for whome Willy served for 34 years threw him away with these remarks "I cannot get blood from stones".

Raymond William (1971) a critic considered the *Death of a Salesman* a social expressionist and a natural play. This play is embodied with expressionism. Willy Loman's chain is not as a simple man but it is the picture of a true sale man. He was a man who started his journey from selling goods, has passed away to selling himself. More he says that Miller in this play showed the social accountability of business and the nature of modern business ethics and relations. His characters are not only the image of life but individuals who embodied values in themselves. (p.274). Eric Mottram considers the *Death of a Salesman* as an expressionist play of degradation. There was a continuous war between father and sons. Father wanted to teach his likeness and dislikeness but the sons were not follower of his father. Willy destroyed himself for his family and business. Main continuous theme of this play is also the Man's attachment with sadness and tension. Willy continuously was in tension that resulted in his suicide.

Lawrence Perrine (1974) in his work *Literature: Structure Sound and Sense* discussed the psyche of Ben, Howard and Willy. Ben and Howard believe that hard work and being well liked has no relation with success. Howard got business from inheritance and Ben had got it by chance. Ben wanted to go to Alaska for gold but he stopped in Africa for diamonds. (p.1416). Charley at the burial ceremony of Willy argued that Willy's all actions are at one stream that is to get maximum tears of audience. He criticized Willy for his fake and fruitless dreams but in the Requiem we see Charley speaking these words in favor of Willy "a salesman has got to dream" (p.1470).

3. Theoretical Framework

Hegel's concept of Self-Realization (self awareness) originates from self consciousness. According to him an individual aware himself as a subject before becoming conscious about objects. Subjects are the objects of another subject. Self consciousness is the awareness of another awareness of oneself. It means one can understand himself only by seeing himself through the eyes of others. He tries to judge what others think about him. So this self realization is not a concrete thing but is a continuous struggle for recognition. This struggle exists between two opposing forces; one is servant and second is lord. When both come together then self consciousness becomes possible. One thinks about oneself by keeping the second at the point of otherness. These both tendencies; selfness and otherness are like the life and death struggle, which are totally opposite to each other for recognition. This tension between self and otherness occurs when both are socially interconnected in an unequal relation of interdependency. One acts as bondsman and other as a lord. The servant acts as the object for his lord rather than a subject (self aware-being). And lord never considers the servant as a subject. The lord continuously remains in a position of superiority while the servant continuously remains in a position of otherness for his lord. The lord opposes his own otherness in the eyes of servant; he rejects the basic impulse toward recognizing the bondsman as a consciousness equal to his own status. On the other hand the servant derives his satisfaction in service; a process of working on and transforming objects through which he rediscovers himself and can claim a "mind of his own".

The self of an individual subsists perpetually in the mind and soul. To realize the self is utmost reality. This reality can be known by inner knowledge. Knowing and realizing self depends upon the person who seeks for self-realization having firm faith on his identity. Realizing self is true state other conditions are nothing just illusions. Self-realization is the truth of reality. Reality is the self-knowledge that is pure consciousness. External forces always modify an individual's knowledge but these are not permanent for a seeker of self. For some instants in ignorance the seeker may follow the illusory external forces but these do not bend his way from getting his goal on his own. Ignorance is the product of "I" and "This". "I" means the self and "This" means the world. Through his knowledge the seeker discriminates between reality and illusions.

3.1. Self-Realization and Ego

Ego is the Spirit which pushes a man to do some work and takes hard steps. It does not differentiate between good and bad, it only make energetic to us. Mind set a path for choosing good or bad; finding truth or living in illusions.

3.2. Self-Realization and spirit

Hegel writes in *Phenomenology of Spirit* about lord and bondsman and their recognition from each other. The evolution of spirit is a continuous process which develops psychologically. The images of lord and bondsman are interoperated throughout life. As we find our self sometimes as an objectifying lord and sometimes objectifying bondsman. The struggle for recognition between bondsman and lord inspired Marx's description of how class struggle obviously arises from the flare-up of one class by the other. The philosophers of twentieth century, including existentialists and psychoanalysts have pinched Hegel's ideas in their works. Kant had also pointed out the difference between subject and object but according to Hegel's point of view subject is the self, is aware it's self only as a typical entity through the eyes of another self. One cannot estimate the concept of self without experiencing the instant of recognition with others. People will become aware about themselves through the image of others. The icon can be positive or negative; depending upon who that person is, where he is standing and what is his position in society. M.W. Steinberg while discussing about the tragic aspects of Miller says that our modern ethical and social system is faulty. Its Pillars are standing on illusions. It is not safe and sound for an idealist person. Therefore our social environment keeps an individual away from realizing himself. Corrigan also commented on Miller's sense about modern man. According to him modern man is bound within chains of life and he tries his best to be himself but chains are so strong that he cannot get rid of them.

3.3. Nature of the Research

The present work on this research will make this research energetic and explanatory to fulfill the aims of the research. Basically it intends to explain the Hegel's concept of self realization in the context of self knowledge, self awareness, desires, relation between bondsman and servant; the opposing forces and cognitive development. The elaboration lies in the critical approach of Hegel in the monarchy of spirit and mind of the characters in *Death of a Salesman*.

3.4. Method of Data Collection

To fulfill the aims of the research and keeping the nature of the research for the characters of Arthur Miller in *Death of a Salesman*, data is totally qualitative and descriptive in nature. The data which is going to be analyzed in this research consists of references from text of Miller's well-known play *Death of a Salesman* which are related with the Hegelian Self-Realization. The mandatory material has been composed by using all the available sources of study. All the scenes and characters of *Death of a Salesman* who modified their lives and affected the others are discussed deeply from the Hegel's point of view of self realization. During the study of play the society and opposing forces are discussed and analyzed; due to that the particular characters think for their self.

4. Analysis

Arthur Miller's *Death of a Salesman* is embodied with Hegel's theory of Self Realization; which arises by self consciousness, self knowledge and self awareness. These all things appear when spirit and desire to get some goal arise. When a man struggles to get something in his life then by comparing himself with others he tries to find his real worth in the eyes of others and his status in the society.

During the discussion of "*Self and Other*" Hegel elaborated the self realization from the self knowledge. It is our mind which reads the faces of others and knows about the others then through our self knowledge we study our inner soul, after that we compare us with others. Every individual thinks about his personality and value as a philosopher and this thinking power vary from individual to individual because the intelligence level varies from person to person. Then thought also changes. Pure thought is mind. So the intelligence is totally cognitive. It is a universal matter not of a particular individual. And the thought is its product which is the identity of subjectivity and objectivity. When every person completed the study of both sides then he starts to realize himself, either he is good or worse in the society. He justifies his position in his environment. Some people accept those norms of society and live happily in illusions but some struggle to justify their arguments about their superiority.

Self Realization may be achieved at different levels. When a man gets an experience in his life and sees the aftermaths of his experience then he gets the full knowledge and goes close to reality. Man's self development is a long journey through adventures, dangers and difficulties. That experience shows the true picture of self personality. Maslow (1959) called that experience the "peak experience". Man's personal awareness at such level that one becomes so fascinated by the super consciousness reality, so deeply absorbed in it, so identified with its different aspects as to lose or paralyze the urge to reach at the level of self realization. More Hegelian Self Realization discusses the knowledge about one's self and worth in the society. If one person finds truth about himself then he is the good finder of himself. Truth is not an objective thing but a subjective thing.

Hegel's fourth chapter of the "*Phenomenology of Spirit*" devoted to self consciousness and the truth of self certainty. A man can feel the original taste of truth about himself when he face the adventures of falsehood and deceive. Hegel also states that self consciousness is achieved only through the satisfaction of another self consciousness. A man can realize himself truly when others keep him at his level.

The courage to face the reality, power and spirit are the basic conditions of philosophy. Due to spirit a man must consider himself worthy of everything that is most sublime. He can never in actual form overestimate the greatness and power of his spirit. If he has faith in his spirit nothing will be so recalcitrant and hard to hide from him. In the "*Phenomenology of Spirit*" there is a phenomenon of personal identity. Personal identity means the self that comes before our mind cannot be conceived as an substantial entity related with a fixed identity. Unlike a fixed identity the self is never simple this or that. Identity in itself is the negation of negation. Hegel says it an *Infinite self reflected and self moving being*. Identity is not something that is achieved easily but it is obtained through a long journey. One reached at the level of self realization when he knows the truth about his existence in the world. The recognition of truth makes a man to take a hard step in his life. Same case is in *The Death of a Salesman*. The protagonist realizes himself and his true worth in the eyes of others then he crashed his car on the road and left the world forever.

More Hegel says that one who wants to recognize himself must put his life in risk otherwise he will remain unaware from truth. And self realization is a natural phenomenon which exists in all individuals. But some people can understand or try to understand this phenomenon. In this an individual considers him superior and single significant entity in the universe. While in the junction of society this individual can be seen as a rational subject of the society by doing different social jobs and activities. "The individual who has not risked his life may well be recognized as a person but he has not attained the truth of this recognition as an independent self-consciousness" (PS114)

4.1. Hegelian Self-Realization and Responses of Miller's Characters in *Death of a Salesman*

4.1.1. Willy Loman

Willy Loman the protagonist is embodied with self-realization in his character and actions. First of all, he realized himself as a successful salesman but gradually he realized his inner self that he has no place in this society. To survive from the shame, he liked to go to death instead of living a poor life. To some extent his society is responsible for his failure. But at broad level his spirit of success according to his own mind and knowledge that deny the forces of society leads him towards tragic death. His state of mind is very furious. He thinks that he is thrown out from the race of life. He has no part in this universe. In this life of competition, he has made his own ways of life for success and to be prominent. This whole life is embodied with his own self-made views which are totally different from social norms. At last, he tires from the war of life and likes death instead of living bourgeois life because he has realized his self.

At the start of his career, he thinks that he is important for his company but the situation was inverse; company was important for him. "I'm the New England man. I'm vital in New England". (Miller 75). At the end this thought leads to him towards self-worth. When he comes home from a long drive he tells Linda, "I'm tired to death".(Miller 74).

He tried to escape from the chain of life several times before but could not do so. Linda asked him to go to his employer for a job in New York then his inner self speaks such words “They don’t need me in New York, I’m the New England man. I’m vital in New England”. (p. 75). At every step he keeps his self before. He never bowed before anyone. When Charley offers him a job and a trip to California then Willy’s and Charley’s conversation comes in this way.

C HARLEY: Oh. (Pause.) I’d like to take a trip to California.

WILLY: Don’t say.

C HARLEY: You want a job?

WILLY: I got a job, I told you that. (After a slight pause.) What the hell are you offering me a job for?

C HARLEY: Don’t get insulted.

WILLY: Don’t insult me.

CHARLEY: I don’t see no sense in it. You don’t have to go on this way.

WILLY: I got a good job. (p.100).

Although Willy has no proper job but to keep his moral high he denied the job. According to him only salesmanship is a well reputed and well payable job. When Willy goes to Howard for a job in New York, instead of wandering on roads. On his entrance Howard started to play with his children. He gave no attention to him. First of all for Willy salesmanship was a good job but now he came to Howard for begging a city job. Howard said him you have worried me, what is the matter with you. Willy replied I tell you the truth that I cannot drive more, then Howard replied we have a road business only and you are a road man. Few persons are working here. Willy begged him that I am not demanding a favour dear. I need only fifty or sixty dollars a week. I am working here when your father brought you here in his arms. But Howard replied “No, but it’s a business, kid, and everybody’s gotta pull his own weight”. Then Willy tells him that when I was of eighteen, nineteen years old I had a question in my mind that selling is a good job and has a bright future. There was a respect and gratitude in those days but now it’s all cut and dried. There is no friendship and gratification now a days. Then he asked him only forty dollars a week. Howard replied him “Kid, I can’t take blood from a stone”. Willy tells him I have served thirtyfour years in this firm, Howard, and now I cannot pay my insurance. Howard, “You can’t eat the orange and throw the peel away-a man is not a piece of fruit”. (p.131). Howard; pull yourself together. Willy; pull myself together.

When Charley again enters then they both start conversation with each other. Then he offers a job to Willy for second time but Willy refuses. After some time Willy begged to him to pay his insurance.

WILLY: Charley, look... (With difficulty.) I got my insurance to pay. If you can manage it — I need a hundred and ten dollars.(p. 142).

Charley became ready to pay him according to his need. Now Willy tells him all that he has realized in his life. Ironically, he was confidential about his deeds but he has realized his worth and the person to whom he believed. He expresses his self before Charley in these words.

WILLY: Charley, I’m strapped. I’m strapped. I don’t know what to do. I was just fired.

C HARLEY: Howard fired you?

WILLY: That snotnose. Imagine that? I named him. I named him Howard.

C HARLEY: Willy, when’re you gonna realize that them things don’t mean anything? You named him Howard, but you can’t sell that. The only thing you got in this world is what you can sell. And the funny thing is that you’re a salesman, and you don’t know that.

WILLY: I’ve always tried to think otherwise, I guess. I always felt that if a man was impressive, and well liked, that nothing... (p. 143,144).

Willy has his own ideals for his success. He continuously remains in his search of his truth of life and truth of being oneself. Therefore he says to Biff “See Biff, everybody around me is so false that I’m constantly lowering my ideals” (Miller 221). This statement reveals the truth for which Willy was wondering. For him every person is living in illusions and they also are culminating me with illusions.

4.1.2. Biff Loman

Biff is another character which is embodied with self-realization. He himself accepts his original value. He was that Biff who was follower of his father and believed in well liked personality for success. In the start of his career he believed to be No. 1 but when a girl rejects him then he shows his real personality before his brother; Happy in these words.

Biff: How the hell did I ever get the idea I was a salesman there? I even believed myself that I’d been a salesman for him! And then he gave me one look and — I realized what a ridiculous lie my whole life has been! We’ve been talking in a dream for fifteen years. I was a shipping clerk. (p. 149).

When Biff returned from Oliver; whom Willy thought his bossom friend and inquired about the appointment then Biff gives a good answer to his father in these words “Everytime I’ve left it’s been a fight that sent me out of here. Today I realized something about myself and I tried to explain it to you and I — I think

I’m just not smart enough to make any sense out of it for you”.(p. 170)

when both Willy and Biff were rejected by the society and faced difficulties then they realized themselves. Angrily Willy blames Biff that it is your fault that you could not make good in your school and you stole things. In reverse Biff blames his father that it is your fault that you had never asked us to make good. Again Willy tells them we have never told and hear the truth for a short while in our house. Everybody was living a life of dreams and illusion. They thought that they will get good job and success because they have well liked personality but the situation was oppose to it. When they returned empty handed in their house then they realize their value personally. Only to keep their moral high in the society they tell others that they are doing good jobs but they were empty handed. When they realized each other’s and themselves then they blame each other for their failure.

B IFF : I stole myself out of every good job since high school!

WILLY: And whose fault is that?

B IFF : And I never got anywhere because you blew me so full of hot air I could never stand taking orders from anybody! That’s whose fault it is!

BIFF: I say I know who I am! Why can’t I say that, Willy? (p. 173).

Again Biff tells his father about his inner self and same things to his father. His father again tries to impose his experience on him and tells him there are many doors which are open before you. You can choose any way for success then Biff replied, “: Pop! I’m a dime a dozen, and so are you!” (Miller 174). They both came in the situation of fight. Biff seems to beat his father. He tells his father that you were only a hard-working drummer. Willy calls Biff a malicious mut and in dreadful condition he walks down to the stairs. Biff in wrath cries “Pop, I’m nothing! I’m nothing, Pop. Can’t you understand that? There’s no spite in it any more. I’m just what I am, that’s all.” (Miller 174). Linda motivates his husband about the love of his sons. Aggression of Willy become cool then boys go to sleep and same Linda asks Willy to sleep but he asks her to take some rest and to settle his mind. Though Willy was tired but his sense of self has reached at peak due to that he was uncomfortable. He could not sleep. Willy instead of going upstairs, he drives his car outside of his house and crashes that. He has put himself to death because he has realized that in this age he has no place in this world.

Secondly Willy Loman was combating with the social forces. He has some personal values for which he was trying to get those but was impossible. He was mutually interconnected with Howard. Both shows its own identity and wants to keep its dignity high. Howard has already master mentality so he realizes himself superior. On the other hand Willy Loman was fighting his own identity. At the start of his life he realized himself illusionary as a superman but at the end his tragic death shows that he has realized the real truth of his life which does not allow him to live an appalling life. He realized that though he cannot earn a lot in life and cannot compete the society and sacrificed his life for his sons so they would get twenty thousand Dollars of his insurance money which will upgrade their morale in society.

4.1.3. Linda Loman

Linda the obliging wife of Willy Loman was very energetic. She supports the Willy Loman at every spot of life. She cared her husband in all his worries. At the start she thought that Willy is doing best for himself and his family. She will get goal in his life but the situation was becoming from bad to worse. Howard has also put him away. When Ben offered a job to Willy then he replied I am making a good. Again he claimed what are you building then Willy says to Linda it is true; nothing is happening. She first time accepts the reality of her husband’s life.

WILLY: Sure, sure. I am building something with this firm, Ben, and if a man is building something he must be on the right track, mustn’t he?

BEN: What are you building? Lay your hand on it. Where is it?

WILLY: (hesitantly): That’s true, Linda, there’s nothing.(p. 134).

5. Conclusion

Throwing light on the meanings and concepts of the sources of self realization the researcher has tried to explain the man’s struggle for self dignity and being superior and independent. Being a philosophical writer Miller elaborated his characters to meet the Hegelian Self-Realization from all perspectives. The first title of this play *The Inside of His Mind* also suggests that mostly actions took place in Willy’s mind. Mind is the sole proprietor of a person deeds. Brain Parker while discussing the social impacts on Willy Loman said he is living in such a society which is ruining him and his family. His society does not allow him to do some more for happy life.

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